

Algebraic Model Counting for Global Analysis of Optimal Decision Trees

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Abstract. Ensuring model reliability in Explainable AI requires a global assessment of the hypothesis space. We propose a formal framework for the exhaustive analysis of optimal and near-optimal decision trees, called *Algebraic Decision Tree Counting* (ADTC). Inspired by Algebraic Model Counting (AMC) in knowledge representation, ADTC reformulates diverse analytical tasks, such as optimization, counting, and sampling, into a unified sum-of-products computation over a semiring R . While the hypothesis space of decision trees is doubly exponential with respect to the maximum depth Δ , our dynamic programming algorithm achieves $O^*(n^{O(\Delta)})$ time complexity in the number of features n , where O^* suppresses polynomial factors. To handle complex constraints consisting of multiple tree metrics, we introduce *model behavior tensors* that aggregate semiring values via convolution products over a tensor semiring. This algebraic approach efficiently constructs a model profile that captures the global landscape and trade-offs between criteria such as accuracy, size, and fairness. We demonstrate the utility of our software, `emtrees`, on real-world datasets, illustrating how ADTC facilitates evidence-based model selection in sensitive domains.

Keywords: algebraic model counting · decision trees · model behavior tensors · predictive multiplicity · algorithmic fairness · global assessment

1 Introduction

Explainable AI (XAI) [28] has placed a growing emphasis on *decision trees* [9] due to their inherent interpretability. However, the phenomenon of *predictive multiplicity* [7, 24], where multiple models achieve similar performance but offer different explanations, poses a significant challenge for model reliability. To address this, we propose *Algebraic Decision Tree Counting* (ADTC), a framework that performs a global assessment of the entire hypothesis space rather than identifying a single heuristic solution.

Our ADTC is inspired by *algebraic model counting* (AMC) proposed by De Raedt and Kimmig [22] in knowledge representation [12]. AMC is an instance of the algebraic computation paradigm (see, e.g., Aji and McEliece [2], Eiter and Kiesel [16], and Goral [17]) that generalizes logical counting by evaluating formulas over a semiring. Specifically, our framework aggregates behaviors of near-optimal prediction models based on a dataset and a constraint formula, whereas AMC aggregates weights of satisfying assignments for a given formula. In this context, *near-optimal models* (or *good models*) [13, 23, 24, 27] refer to those within the *Rashomon set* [8, 28, 32] that satisfy a predefined performance threshold relative to the empirical best model.

Fig. 1: Model profiles of 34,706 decision trees with $\text{maxdep} = 5$ and $\text{relminsup} = 0.15$ from the Rashomon set on the `adult` dataset generated by ADTC, showing (a) trade-off between Accuracy and F1-score, and (b) model multiplicity between Accuracy and DP-gap. See Fig. 7 for more examples and Sec. 5.4 for explanation.

Conceptually, the framework ADTC executes an “*enumerate-filter-aggregate*” style query over the huge hypothesis space of decision trees, similar to analytic queries in relational databases [6]. While the number of syntactically distinct decision trees is $n^{\Theta(2^\Delta)}$, our approach achieves a time complexity of $O^*(n^\Delta)$, which is polynomial in data size n but exponential in query size Δ , by employing a dynamic programming scheme based on tensor operations. Consequently, our framework *avoids the double-exponential complexity* of exhaustive enumeration through algebraic aggregation.

The primary contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- **Algebraic framework for decision trees:** In Sec. 2, we propose ADTC, a unified framework based on algebraic model counting [16, 22], to evaluate and aggregate decision trees over arbitrary commutative semirings. It provides a comprehensive perspective that generalizes previous studies on *induction* [1, 26, 27], *enumeration* [29], *counting* as well as *sampling* [4, 32], and *Pareto optimization* [13] of optimal decision trees, which have often been treated independently.
- **Theoretical complexity guarantees:** In Sec. 3, we develop a dynamic programming (DP) algorithm EMT using tensor operations (Algorithm 1) that achieves a running time of $O^*(n^{O(\Delta)})$ with fixed metrics (Theorem 3). This complexity is polynomial in data size n , although exponential in query size Δ , avoiding the double-exponential bottleneck of exhaustive enumeration. The key to this efficiency lies in aggregating values of multiple metrics, such as `size` and `error` of decision trees, into a semiring of *model behavior tensors*, that allow for efficient computation via DP over a *factorized representation* of the decision tree space. In Sec. 4, we extend EMT to *nonlinear metrics* [13] as well as *model sampling* [4, 17].
- **Transparent model profiling:** In Sec. 5, we demonstrate that our framework enables global navigation of the rashomon set, facilitating transparent and rigorous analysis of *trade-offs between multiple objectives*, such as the *accuracy* and *F1-score* in Fig. 1, and *assessment of preprocessing*, such as the *original* and *balanced*

(a) Original `adult` dataset.(b) Balanced version of `adult` dataset.

Fig. 2: Model profiles of 34,706 decision trees with $\text{maxdep} = 5$ and $\text{relminsup} = 0.15$ from the Rashomon set on the `adult` dataset generated by ADTC on assessment of preprocessing with accuracy and balanced accuracy. See Sec. 5.5 for explanation.

accuracy in Fig. 2 (in Sec. 5). This profiling addresses diverse requirements in real-world machine learning deployments. Finally, we conduct empirical evaluations of our `emtrees` software [3], an implementation of the EMT algorithm in Secs. 3 and 4, on the standard benchmark UCI `adult` dataset to demonstrate its scalability and effectiveness in global analysis tasks for sensitive domains.

Overall, this proposed framework enables a global navigation of the Rashomon set, allowing ADTC to analyze the trade-offs between multiple objectives, such as accuracy and fairness. By providing a rigorous profile of all near-optimal models, our framework facilitates transparent and rigorous model selection for diverse requirements in real-world machine learning deployments.

1.1 Related Work

The global analysis of decision tree spaces intersects with several research areas, including optimal decision tree construction, model counting, and the study of the Rashomon set.

Optimal decision tree construction. Recent advancements have introduced exact algorithms such as GOSDT [23] and DL8.5 [1]. While these methods excel at finding a single optimal tree [26, 27], they are not designed to characterize the entire landscape of near-optimal models. In contrast, our approach enables a comprehensive aggregation of these models through a unified algebraic framework.

The Rashomon set and predictive multiplicity. Previous work by Dong and Rudin [14] explored the Rashomon set [28] via *sampling*, while Xin *et al.* [32] utilized *compressed representations*. However, the latter requires *exponential memory* and is primarily limited to counting [32]. In contrast, our approach employs model behavior tensors computable in *polynomial space* (see Theorem 3). Within a unified semiring-based

framework of ADTC, we provide an *exact profile* of model diversity that reveals the underlying *predictive multiplicity* and *trade-offs*, enabling various analytical tasks beyond simple counting.

Algebraic model counting. Our work bridges the gap between *Algebraic Model Counting* (AMC) [22] and the *combinatorial space of decision trees* by adapting the AMC paradigm to the *recursive structure of trees*. This allows for efficient *sum-of-product computations* [16,17] over tensors, avoiding the *double-exponential bottlenecks* associated with naive enumeration.

2 Preliminaries

The following notation and terminology are used throughout this paper. For standard terminology not defined below, please consult [20] for machine learning, [11] for algorithms, [15] for logic, and [10] for algebraic computation.

2.1 Basic Definitions

Numbers, sets, and vectors. Let \mathbb{R} , \mathbb{Q} , and $\mathbb{N} = \{0, 1, \dots\}$ be the sets of all real numbers, rational numbers, and natural numbers, respectively. For an integer n , $i, j \in \mathbb{N}$ with $i \leq j$, we define $[n] = \{1, \dots, n\}$, and $[i..j] = \{i, i+1, \dots, j\} \subseteq \mathbb{N}$. For any sets A and B , $|A|$ denotes the *cardinality* of A , 2^A the power set of A , and A^* the set of all finite sequences of elements from A . The notation B^A denotes the set of all mappings from A to B . For $d \in \mathbb{N}$, we write d -vector $\mathbf{x} = (x_j)_{j=1}^d$ as $(x_j)_d$. For $d \in \mathbb{N}$ and a d -vector $\mathbf{m} = (m_1, \dots, m_d) \in \mathbb{N}^d$, let $\mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]$ denote $[m_1] \times \dots \times [m_d] \subseteq \mathbb{N}^d$.

Semirings and polynomials. A *monoid* (M, \cdot, e) is a set M equipped with an associative binary operation \cdot and an identity $e \in M$. It is commutative if $a+b = b+a$ holds. A *semiring* is an algebraic structure $\mathcal{R} = (R, +, \cdot, \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1})$, where $a \cdot b$ is written ab , and (i) $(R, +, \mathbf{0})$ is a commutative monoid, (ii) $(R, \cdot, \mathbf{1})$ is a monoid, (iii) The multiplication \cdot *distributes* over addition $+$: $a(b+c) = (ab)+(ac)$ and $(a+b)c = (ac)+(bc)$, and (iv) $\mathbf{0}$ is *absorbing*, i.e., $\mathbf{0}a = a\mathbf{0} = \mathbf{0}$ for all $a, b, c \in R$. In this work, we mainly consider commutative semirings. For $d \in \mathbb{N}$ and a semiring R , we denote by $R[(x_j)_d]$ the semiring of d -variate polynomials with coefficients in R . Each polynomial in $R[(x_j)_d]$ with indeterminates $x = (x_j)_d$ is represented as $p(x) = \sum_{\mathbf{v}} c_{\mathbf{v}} x^{\mathbf{k}} = \sum_{\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{N}^d} c_{\mathbf{v}} \prod_{j=1}^d x_j^{v_j}$, where $c_{\mathbf{v}} \in R$. These structures are fundamental for *algebraic model counting* [22]. A *rational function* is a fraction of multi-variate polynomials of the form $P(x)/Q(x)$.¹

2.2 Prediction Models and Their Behaviors

Decision trees. Let \mathcal{X} be a universe of *data*. We assume n *Boolean features* $F = \{f_1\}_{i=1}^n$ and c *categorical labels* $L = \{y_j\}_{j=0}^{c-1}$, where each Boolean feature is a mapping $f : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$. A *decision tree* (a *tree*, for short) over alphabets $\Sigma = (F, L)$ is an expression represented as a node-labeled binary tree. A tree t and its *string notation*

¹ Rational functions are closed under addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division by non-zero functions [10].

are defined inductively as follows: t is either (i) a leaf labeled with $y \in L$, denoted by y itself, or (ii) a composite tree with a root labeled with a feature f in F having two children t_0 and t_1 , denoted by $\langle f, t_0, t_1 \rangle$. A tree t induces a *prediction function* $f_t : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ that, given a data $x \in \mathcal{X}$, returns a prediction label $y = f_t(x) \in L$ via a standard root-to-leaf traversal. A *sample* is a set of data $S = \{x_i\}_{i=1}^m$ in $2^{\mathcal{X}}$. An *input data* is a pair (S, y) of a sample S and a *labeling function* $y : S \rightarrow L$. For any leaf λ of a tree t , $S(\lambda)$ denotes the subset of S consisting of all data that fall into λ .

Hypothesis spaces: We consider the hypothesis space \mathcal{M}_Δ of *all decision trees with depth at most $\Delta \geq 0$* over a given alphabet $\Sigma = (F, L)$ because the complexity is primarily governed by depth [26]. The number of syntactically distinct Boolean trees in \mathcal{M}_Δ is $n^{\Theta(2^\Delta)}$, which exhibits double-exponential growth. While \mathcal{M}_Δ serves as our baseline, we can further restrict it by imposing $\text{minsup} = \mu$ (*minimum support*) and $\text{nbins} = b$ (*number of discretization bins*), denoted as $\mathcal{M}_{\Delta, \mu, b}$, for pruning [23, 27].

2.3 Model Behavior Metrics

We will analyze the hypothesis space \mathcal{M}_Δ of models by means of measuring functions, called *model metrics* (or *metrics*). Let $\Delta \in \mathbb{N}$. In our global analysis of decision tree space \mathcal{M}_Δ , a smallest unit of analysis is a pair (t, S) of a tree $t \in \mathcal{M}_\Delta$ and a sample $S \in 2^{\mathcal{X}}$, called a *structure*. We call the product $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{M}_\Delta \times 2^{\mathcal{X}}$ the *domain of structures*. Then, a *model metrics* (or *metrics*) is any mapping $\sigma : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \text{dom}(\sigma)$ that assigns a value $k = \sigma(t, S) \in \mathcal{S}$ to each model $t \in \mathcal{M}_\Delta$, where $\text{dom}(\sigma)$ is any set. A metric σ is said to be *primitive* if it has an integer-valued range $\text{dom}(\sigma) = [0..m_\sigma]$, where $m_\sigma \in \mathbb{N}$ is called the *maximum range*.

The following are examples of primitive metrics used in this paper. (i) *Structural metrics:* The *size*, $\text{size}(t) = |Lv(t)|$, is defined to be the number of leaves, and the *depth*, $\text{dep}(t)$, is the number of edges in the path from the root to the deepest leaf, respectively, with ranges $1 \leq \text{size}(t) \leq 2^\Delta$ and $0 \leq \text{dep}(t) \leq \Delta$. (ii) *Semantic metrics:* Given an input data $D = (S, y)$, the *error*, $\text{error}(t, S) = \sum_{x \in S} \mathbb{1}[\phi_t(x) \neq y(x)]$, measures predictive performance, and the *support*, $\text{supp}(t, S) = \min_{\lambda \in Lv(t)} |S(\lambda)|$, captures the statistical reliability of leaf nodes. In Sec. 4.1, we will introduce primitive metrics related to contingency tables as well as complex nonlinear metrics.

To devise efficient algorithms for ADTC, we need to introduce the notion of decomposition of a metric, in a similar way to AMC [17, 22]. For any feature $f \in F$, we define the *split* of a data set S by f to be the partition $S = S_{f=1} \uplus S_{f=0}$ such that $S_{f=i} = \{x \in S \mid f(x) = i\}$ for each $i \in \{0, 1\}$. Def. 1 below generalizes [26, 27].

Definition 1 (Decomposable metrics). A function $f : \mathcal{M}_\Delta \times 2^{\mathcal{X}} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ over the domain of structures $\mathcal{M}_\Delta \times 2^{\mathcal{X}}$ is *decomposable* on tree structures if there exists some monoid $(\mathbb{N}, \circ, 0)$ such that f satisfies the recurrence:

$$f(t, S) = \begin{cases} \underline{f}(y, S) & \text{if } t = y \in L, \\ \overline{f}(t_1, S_{f=1}) \circ \overline{f}(t_0, S_{f=0}) & \text{if } t = \langle f, t_1, t_0 \rangle, S = S_{f=1} \uplus S_{f=0}, \end{cases}$$

where (i) $\underline{f} : L \times 2^{\mathcal{X}} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is the restriction of f to $L \times 2^{\mathcal{X}}$, called the (*leaf*) *labeling function*, and (ii) $\circ : \mathbb{N}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is a binary operator over \mathbb{N} . Then, we say that f is *decomposable via operator \circ* , denoted $f = \text{Hom}[\underline{f}, \circ]$.

2.4 Constraint Formulas and ϕ -Good Models

In the global analysis of decision trees, it is standard practice to investigate a subspace of the hypothesis space consisting of high-quality models, or *good models* [24, 28], called the *Rashomon set*, such that $\text{size}(t) \leq s$ and $\text{error}(t, S) \leq e$. We generalize this notion below. For any $d \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\mathbf{m} = (m_i)_d \in \mathbb{N}^d$, a *rank- d combination operator of shape \mathbf{m}* is any d -vector $\sigma : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]$ of primitive metrics, where $\sigma = (\sigma_i)_d$.

We introduce the *syntax* of constraint formulas as follows. The *vocabulary* with a rank- d combination operator $\sigma : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]$ includes constants for numbers in \mathbb{N} and \mathbb{R} , nullary variables $\tilde{\sigma} = (\tilde{\sigma}_i)_d$, binary operators $+$, \times , (\cdot) , and a binary relation symbol \leq . Terms are rational expressions constructed from all constants, operators, and function variables $\tilde{\sigma}$. An atomic formula is either $(f(\tilde{\sigma}) \leq c)$ or $(f(\tilde{\sigma}) \leq g(\tilde{\sigma}))$ with rational expressions f, g and constants c . Then, the set of *constraint formulas* consists of all formulas with free variables $\tilde{\sigma}$ constructed from atomic formulas $\phi[\tilde{\sigma}]$ using Boolean operations \neg, \vee, \wedge . For example, the followings are constraint formulas

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_1 &= (\text{size} \leq 4) \wedge (\text{error} \leq 0.05 \cdot N), & \phi_2 &= (\text{acc} \geq 0.9) \wedge (\text{f1} \geq 0.76) \\ &\text{with } \text{acc} := (N_{1,1} + N_{0,0})/N, & \text{f1} &:= (2 \cdot N_{1,1}) / (2 \cdot N_{1,1} + N_{0,0} + N_{1,0}), \end{aligned}$$

where ϕ_1 states that t is accurate and succinct on S , while ϕ_2 states that t has high scores in both accuracy and F1. Metrics $\text{acc}, \text{f1}, \{N_{i,j}\}$ will be introduced in Sec. 4.1.

We define the *semantics* of constraint formulas as follows: We consider a pair $(t, S) \in \mathcal{S} = \mathcal{M}_\Delta \times 2^{\mathcal{X}}$ as a *structure* over the vocabulary. Then, a d -metric vector $\sigma = (\sigma_i)_d$ assigns to the structure (t, S) in \mathcal{S} a d -integer vector $\mathbf{k} = \sigma(t, S) \in \mathbb{N}^d$, called the *index* of t , where $\mathbf{k} = (k_i)_d$ and $k_i = \sigma_i(t, S)$ for all $i \in [d]$. Given a formula $\phi = \phi[\tilde{\sigma}]$, we write $(t, S) \models \phi$ if ϕ evaluates true under valuation $\tilde{\sigma} \mapsto \sigma(t, S) \in \mathbb{N}^d$ with the standard interpretation of logical connectives [15]. Then, we say that a decision tree $t \in \mathcal{M}_\Delta$ is a *ϕ -good model* on S if $(t, S) \models \phi$. Note that the truth of ϕ on the structure (t, S) is solely determined by the vector $\mathbf{k} = \sigma(t, S)$ in \mathbb{N}^d . We define the *hypothesis space of ϕ -good models* by $\mathcal{M}_\Delta(\phi, S) = \{t \in \mathcal{M}_\Delta \mid (t, S) \models \phi\}$.

2.5 Our Problem: Algebraic Decision Tree Counting

From now on, we define our problem, ADTC, the algebraic decision tree counting over a semiring $(R, +_R, \cdot_R, \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1})$. Recall that $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{M}_\Delta \times 2^{\mathcal{X}}$ is the domain of structures.

Definition 2 (Aggregation). An *aggregation operator* over R is any function $\alpha : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow R$ that assigns an element $\alpha(t, S) \in R$ to each structure $(t, S) \in \mathcal{S}$.

Then, a *rank- d query* is a tuple $Q = (\Delta, \alpha, \sigma, \phi[\sigma])$ consisting of (i) $\Delta \in \mathbb{N}$, (ii) an aggregation operator $\alpha : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow R$, (iii) a rank- d combination operator $\sigma : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]$ with $\mathbf{m} \in \mathbb{N}^d$, and (iv) a constraint formula $\phi = \phi[\sigma]$ over σ . An *input data* $D = (S, y)$ is a pair of a sample S and a label function $y : S \rightarrow L$. We state our problem.

Definition 3 (ADTC). The ALGEBRAIC DECISION TREE COUNTING over a semiring R is the problem of, given a rank- d query $Q = (\Delta, \alpha, \sigma, \phi[\sigma])$ and an input data

$D = (S, y)$, computing the semiring element

$$\text{ADTC}(Q, D) = \sum_{t \in \mathcal{M}_\Delta: (t, S) \models \phi[\sigma]} \alpha(t, S) \in R, \quad (1)$$

that is, the *summation of the aggregation value* $\alpha(t, S)$ with $+_R$ over all ϕ -good trees t within \mathcal{M}_Δ relative to a sample S .

By varying a semiring $(R, +_R, \cdot_R)$ and a query Q as its components, the ADTC problem can naturally formulate a wide range of global analytics tasks as follows. Let $\text{one}(t, S) = \mathbf{1}$ be the aggregation operator that always returns the constant $\mathbf{1} \in R$.

Lemma 1. *For any $\Sigma = (F, L)$, the framework ADTC can solve the following tasks for the space \mathcal{M}_Δ of decision trees by varying a semiring R and a query Q as follows:*

- (1) *The Boolean ring $(\mathbb{B}, \vee, \wedge, 0, 1)$ with $\alpha = \text{one}$ and $\phi_{\text{good}} = (\text{size} \leq s) \wedge (\text{error} \leq e)$ serves for deciding the existence of a small and accurate decision tree [27].*
- (2) *The natural number ring $(\mathbb{N}, +, \times, 0, 1)$ with $\alpha = \text{one}$ serves for counting all small and accurate decision trees on the arithmetic semiring on natural numbers [4, 32].*
- (3) *The min-plus semiring $(\mathbb{N}, \min, +, \infty, 0)$ serves for finding accurate tree minimizing the error $\alpha_{\text{err}}(t, S) := \text{error}(t, S)$ [4, 29]. Remark that α_{err} is decomposable as $\alpha_{\text{err}}(\langle f, t_1, t_0 \rangle, S) = \alpha_{\text{err}}(t_1, S_{f=1}) + \alpha_{\text{err}}(S, t_0, S_{f=0})$ using $\cdot_R = +$.*

Proof (sketch). The proof is straightforward by discussions similar to [16, 17]. \square

We remark that the complexity of ADTC depends crucially on an underlying semiring R . To be precise, we introduce the parameter t_R and s_R to be the *worst-case time* and *space complexities* for operations on \mathcal{R} . We observe that ADTC can be solved by a straightforward method according to Eq.(1) as follows: it first initializes a variable $r = \mathbf{0} \in R$, then, scans all trees t in \mathcal{M}_Δ , where at each iteration, it evaluates $\sigma(t, S)$, and adds the weight $\alpha(t, S) \in R$ to r if $(t, S) \models \phi[\sigma]$ holds. However, since $|\mathcal{M}_\Delta| = n^{\Theta(2^\Delta)}$, this method requires doubly exponential time in Δ .

3 Efficient Algorithm

This section presents a dynamic programming approach solving ADTC in $O^*(n^{O(\Delta)} \cdot t_R)$ time and $O^*(s_R)$ space over \mathcal{M}_Δ . We first formalize decomposability of metrics (Sec. 3.1), and then develop the EMT algorithm for unconstrained ADTC (Sec. 3.2). Reducing the tensor construction MT to this unconstrained setting (Sec. 3.3) yields our final algorithm for the general constrained ADTC problem (Sec. 3.4).

3.1 Assumptions on Analytic Queries

Let $(R, +_R, \cdot_R, \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1})$ be a semiring. For any integer $d \in \mathbb{N}$ and any d -vector $\mathbf{m} \in \mathbb{N}^d$, a *d-product monoid* is a monoid $\mathcal{A} = (\mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}], \circ, \mathbf{1})$ consisting of (i) $\mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]$, (ii) $\circ = (\circ_i)_d$, and (iii) $\mathbf{1} := (1_i)_d$, obtained by product of d monoids $([0..m_i], \circ_i, 1_i)$, $1 \leq i \leq d$, over truncated integers $\mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}] = ([0..m_i])_d$. Throughout this section, we assume that any rank- d query $Q = (\Delta, \alpha, \sigma, \phi[\sigma])$ with aggregation and rank- d combination operators $\alpha : S \rightarrow R$ and $\sigma : S \rightarrow \mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]$, respectively, satisfies the following conditions (i)–(ii):

Algorithm 1: The recursive procedure that, given an unconstrained query $Q = (\Delta, \alpha)$ and an input $D = (S, y)$ under Assump. 1, solves the unconstrained ALGEBRAIC DECISION TREE COUNTING problem for the class \mathcal{M}_Δ of decision trees over alphabets $\Sigma = (F, L)$ and a semiring $(R, +_R, \cdot_R, \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1})$. It recursively searches the subspace of \mathcal{M}_Δ specified by a triple (Δ, S, F) consisting of a maximum depth Δ , a sample S , and a feature set F .

```

1 Procedure EMT( $\Delta, S, F$ );                                     // Process path  $P$ 
2 begin
3    $\alpha \leftarrow \mathbf{0}$ ;
4   for each label  $\ell \in L$  do
5      $\alpha_{\text{leaf}} \leftarrow \mathbf{1}$ ;
6     for each  $x \in S$  do  $\alpha_{\text{leaf}} \leftarrow (\alpha_{\text{leaf}} \cdot_R \underline{\alpha}(\ell, x))$ ;
7      $\alpha \leftarrow \alpha +_R \alpha_{\text{leaf}}$ ;
8   if  $\Delta = 0$  then
9     return  $\alpha$ ;
10  for each feature  $f \in F$  do
11     $\alpha_1 \leftarrow \text{EMT}(\Delta - 1, S_{f=1}, F \setminus \{f\})$ ;      // Process path  $P \cdot \langle f = 1 \rangle$ 
12     $\alpha_0 \leftarrow \text{EMT}(\Delta - 1, S_{f=0}, F \setminus \{f\})$ ;    // Process path  $P \cdot \langle f = 0 \rangle$ 
13     $\alpha \leftarrow \alpha +_R (\alpha_1 \cdot_R \alpha_0)$ ;
14  return  $\alpha$ ;

```

Assumption 1. (i) The aggregation operator α is decomposable via \cdot_R over R , that is, $\alpha = \text{Hom}[\underline{\alpha}, \cdot_R]$. (ii) There exists a d -product monoid $\mathcal{A} = (\mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}], \circ, \mathbf{1})$ such that the combination operator σ is decomposable via $\circ = (\circ_i)_d$ over $\mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]$, that is, $\sigma = \text{Hom}[\underline{\sigma}, \circ]$.

When the underlying algebraic structures are clear, we simply write α and σ to denote the *decomposable schemas* (α, R) and (σ, \mathcal{A}) , respectively.

3.2 ADTC without Constraints

First, we present our basic algorithm EMT for unconstrained queries of the form $Q = (\Delta, \alpha)$, where metrics σ and constraint formula $\phi[\sigma]$ are empty. Although such restricted queries seem useless in practice, they will turn out to be useful as an important building block of a general ADTC algorithm of Sec. 3.3 and Sec. 3.4.

Definition 4 (Algorithm EMT). We assume an unconstrained rank- d query $Q = (\Delta, \alpha)$ and an input data $D = (S, y)$ satisfying Assump. 1. Then, the procedure EMT is defined by the recurrence below by induction on $\Delta \geq 0$, where arguments S and F are any subsets of initial a sample S_0 and a feature set F_0 :

- (1) In the case with $\Delta = 0$, we let $\text{EMT}(0, S, F) = (\sum_{\ell \in L} \underline{\alpha}(\ell, S))$.
- (2) In the case with $\Delta \geq 1$, we let

$$\text{EMT}(\Delta, S, F) = \text{EMT}(0, S, F) +_R \left(\sum_{f \in F} \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{EMT}(\Delta - 1, S_{f=1}, F \setminus \{f\}) \\ \cdot_R \text{EMT}(\Delta - 1, S_{f=0}, F \setminus \{f\}) \end{array} \right) \right).$$

In Algorithm 1, we present the pseudocode of **EMT** that implements the recurrence of Def. 4, where we assume that α is *homomorphic* on data, i.e., $\underline{\alpha}(\ell, S) = \bigotimes_{x \in S} \underline{\alpha}(\ell, \{x\})$ as it is true with most α in this paper. In the top-level, given $\Sigma = (F, L)$ and an input $D = (S, y)$, the invocation of **EMT** (Δ, S, F) computes a semiring element $v \in R$. By the distributivity of \cdot_R over $+_R$, we can show the next lemma.

Lemma 2 (Correctness of EMT). *Under Assump. 1, given an unconstrained rank- d query $Q = (\Delta, \alpha)$ and an input data $D = (S, y)$, the procedure **EMT** solves the unconstrained **ADTC** problem.*

Proof. In what follows, we write the solution $a(\mathcal{M}_\Delta, S, F)$ of **ADTC** by emphasizing its dependency on S, F in the recurrence. Then, we show the claim that $a(\mathcal{M}_\Delta, S, F)$ coincides with the return value **EMT** (Δ, S, F) of the algorithm (*1).

(1) First, we suppose that $\Delta = 0$. Since $\mathcal{M}_0 = L$ and $\phi = 1$, we have the equations

$$a(\mathcal{M}_0, S, F) = \sum_{\ell \in L} \underline{\alpha}(\ell, S) = \mathbf{EMT}(0, S, F),$$

where the first equality follows from the base case of α with $(\cdot_R, \underline{\alpha})$, and the second equality follows by the definition of **EMT**.

(2) Next, suppose that $\Delta \geq 1$ and the claim holds for all $\Delta' \leq \Delta - 1$. Let $A := a(\mathcal{M}_\Delta, S, F) = \sum_{t \in \mathcal{M}_{0:\Delta}} \alpha(t, D)$ be the solution. Since \mathcal{M}_Δ can be split as $\mathcal{M}_\Delta = \mathcal{M}_{1:\Delta} \uplus \mathcal{M}_0$ such that $\mathcal{M}_{1:\Delta}$ is the subset consisting of all composite trees, if we define

$$A_0 := \sum_{t \in \mathcal{M}_0} \alpha(t, D) = \mathbf{EMT}(0, S, F), \quad A_{1:\Delta} := \sum_{t \in \mathcal{M}_{1:\Delta}} \alpha(t, D),$$

then the solution A equals the summation of $\alpha(t, S)$ over all trees t in \mathcal{M}_Δ , we can decompose A into the sum $A = A_0 \uplus A_{1:\Delta}$ of values A_0 and $A_{1:\Delta}$, where $\mathcal{M}_0 = L$. We see that any pair (t, S) of a composite tree $t = \langle f, t_1, t_0 \rangle \in \mathcal{M}_{1:\Delta}$ and a sample S can be decomposed into smaller problems $(t_1, S_{f=1})$ and $(t_0, S_{f=0})$, where $S = S_{f=1} \uplus S_{f=0}$. Applying the distributivity of \cdot_R over $+_R$, we obtain the following derivation:

$$\begin{aligned} A_{1:\Delta} &= \sum_{t \in \mathcal{M}_{1:\Delta}} \alpha(t, D, F) = \sum_{f \in F} \sum_{t_1} \sum_{t_0} \left(\begin{array}{c} \alpha(t_1, S_{f=1}, F \setminus \{f\}) \\ \cdot_R \alpha(t_0, S_{f=0}, F \setminus \{f\}) \end{array} \right) \\ &= \sum_{f \in F} \sum_{t_1} \left(\alpha(t_1, S_{f=1}, F \setminus \{f\}) \cdot_R C_0 \right) \quad \because \text{left-distributivity of } \cdot_R \\ &= \sum_{f \in F} (C_1 \cdot_R C_0) \quad \because \text{right-distributivity of } \cdot_R \\ &= \sum_{f \in F} \left(\begin{array}{c} \mathbf{EMT}(\Delta - 1, S_{f=1}, F \setminus \{f\}) \\ \cdot_R \mathbf{EMT}(\Delta - 1, S_{f=0}, F \setminus \{f\}) \end{array} \right) \quad \because \text{induction hypothesis} \end{aligned}$$

where t_1, t_0 range over composite trees in \mathcal{M}_{d-1} , $C_0 := \sum_{t_0} \alpha(t_0, S_{f=0})$, and $C_1 := (\sum_{t_1} \alpha(t_1, S_{f=1}))$. As seen above, the left- and right-distributivities are used. The last line follows from the induction hypothesis. Hence, the lemma is proved. \square

Now, we show the first theorem. Recall that O^* notation hides polynomial factors.

Theorem 1 (Complexity of ADTC without constraint). *Let $(R, +_R, \cdot_R)$ be any semiring. Under Assump. 1, given an unconstrained rank- d query $Q = (\Delta, \alpha)$ and an input data $D = (S, y)$, the ADTC problem can be solved in $O^*(n^{O(\Delta)} \cdot t_R)$ time and $O^*(s_R)$ space.*

Proof. The correctness follows from Lemma 2. For the time complexity, we observe that every iteration X of the procedure is specified by the *unique decision path* P in $(F \times \{1, 0\})^*$ shown in Algorithm 1. From this, we see that there are at most $(2|F|)^\Delta |L| \leq 2^\Delta n^\Delta l$ distinct decision paths of length Δ . Since we can charge $O(t_R)$ time for operating on elements of R to each iteration X , we see that the running time is bounded by $O((2^\Delta n^\Delta l)t_R)$. Furthermore, at each intermediate iteration X of depth $\Delta' \leq \Delta$, the procedure stores at most $2^{\Delta'}$ tensors on a stack, each of which occupies $O(N^{ck_{s_R}})$ space. Hence, the total space is $O(\Delta N^{ck_{s_R}})$. This shows the theorem. \square

From Theorem 1, we see that the problem ADTC is computable in polynomial time w.r.t. the size of input D when a query Q is regarded as constant.

3.3 ADTC over a Semiring of Model Behavior Tensors

Next, we present an efficient algorithm for the MODEL BEHAVIOR TENSOR problem. Intuitively, a rank- d *model behavior tensor* (or *model tensor*, MT) is a d -way cross table of aggregation values via α on \mathcal{M}_Δ w.r.t. multiple metrics σ (see Fig. 3(a)). An *MT query* means any rank- d query $Q = (\Delta, \alpha, \sigma)$ with the empty constraint $\phi[\sigma]$.

Behavior of decision trees as tensors. Let $\Delta, d \in \mathbb{N}$ be any integers, and let $(R, +_R, \cdot_R, \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1})$ be any semiring. Let $Q = (\Delta, \alpha, \sigma, \phi[\sigma])$ be any rank- d (analytic) query. Recall that $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{M}_\Delta \times 2^{\mathcal{X}}$ is the domain of structures. Under Assump. 1, we define the *behavior* of each structure $\tau = (t, S) \in \mathcal{S}$ to be the *index-weight pair* (\mathbf{k}, v) computed by $\mathbf{k} = \sigma(t, S) \in \mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]$ and $v = \alpha(t, S) \in R$. For any $d \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\mathbf{m} \in \mathbb{N}^d$, a rank- d tensor T with shape \mathbf{m} is a function $T : \mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}] \rightarrow R$ that assigns a value $T(\mathbf{k}) \in R$ to each index $\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]$ in the d -dim discrete space. Now, we state the second problem of this paper as follows.

Definition 5 (MT problem). Let $(R, +_R, \cdot_R, \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1})$ be any semiring and $(\mathcal{A}, \circ, \mathbf{1})$ be a d -vector of monoids. The MODEL BEHAVIOR TENSOR problem over R (MT) is the problem of, given any rank- d model tensor query $Q' = (\Delta, \alpha, \sigma)$ with decomposition schema (α, R) and (σ, \mathcal{A}) , and input data $D = (S, y)$, computing the rank- d tensor $T \in R^{\mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]}$ such that for every $\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]$, the entry $T(\mathbf{k})$ is defined as

$$T(\mathbf{k}) = \sum_{\substack{t \in \mathcal{M}_\Delta \\ (t, S) \models \phi, \mathbf{k} = \sigma(t, S)}} \alpha(t, S) \in R,$$

where $\sigma(t, S)$ and $\alpha(t, S)$ are the index and value of a structure (t, S) in \mathcal{S} , respectively, and \sum is the summation $+_R$ over R . Then, the tensor T is called the *model behavior tensor* (or a *model tensor*) for (Q', D) and denoted by $\text{MT}[Q, D]$.

A key to efficient algorithms for the problem is a set of operations over model behavior tensors, introduced as follows.

Definition 6 (Tensor operations). We define the following operations. Let $\mathbf{m} \in \mathbb{N}^d$ be any d -vector of integers, and \mathcal{S} be any aggregation scheme with dimension \mathbf{m} .

- (1) The *zero tensor* $\mathbf{0}$ that has zero 0_R everywhere, i.e., $\mathbf{0}(\mathbf{k}) = 0_R$ for all \mathbf{k} .
- (2) The *unity tensor* $\mathbf{1}$ that has a unity 1_R at the zero vector $(0_i)_d$ and zero 0_R elsewhere.
- (3) The *singleton tensor* $T = [i = \mathbf{k}]v$, in *Iverson's notation* with variable i , for a tree-data pair (t, S) that holds a semiring value $v = \alpha(t, S)$ at point $\mathbf{k} = \sigma(t, S)$.
- (4) The point-wise addition $T_1 \oplus T_0$ such that at every point $\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]$, $(T_1 \oplus T_0)(\mathbf{k}) = T_1(\mathbf{k}) +_R T_0(\mathbf{k}) \in R$.
- (5) The (truncated) convolution product $T_1 \otimes T_0$ such that at every point $\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]$,

$$(T_1 \otimes T_0)(\mathbf{k}) = \sum_{\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_0 \in \mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]: \mathbf{k}_1 \circ \mathbf{k}_0 = \mathbf{k}} T_1(\mathbf{k}_1) \cdot_R T_0(\mathbf{k}_0) \in R,$$

where $\mathbf{k}_1, \mathbf{k}_0$ range over $\mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]$, \sum takes $+_R$ on R , and \circ operates on $\mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]$.

In this way, we obtain from any semiring $(R, +_R, \cdot_R, 0_R, 1_R)$ the algebraic structure $(R^{\mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]}, \oplus, \otimes, \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1})$ over the collection $R^{\mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]}$ of rank- d tensors of shape \mathbf{m} . Then the *volume* $V(T)$ of a tensor T in $R^{\mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]}$ is the number of its nonzero entries, and is bounded by $O(m_*^d)$ where $m_* = \max_i m_i$ is called the *maximum range value*.

Decision trees as polynomials. Any model tensor $T \in R^{\mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]}$ maps to a multivariate truncated polynomial $P(x) = \sum_{\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]} T(\mathbf{k})x^{\mathbf{k}}$ over R , where $x = (x_i)_d$ are indeterminates. This establishes a bijection between $R^{\mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]}$ and the quotient semiring $R[(x_i)_d] / \langle x^{m_j} \rangle_{j=1}^d$ bounding each degree to $m_i - 1$.² Division in R is not required.

Lemma 3 (Folklore). *Under the above correspondence, the set of d -variate truncated polynomials modulo $\langle x^{m_j} \rangle_{j=1}^d$ and the set of rank- d tensors with size \mathbf{m} are isomorphic. Specifically, the addition and product of polynomials coincide with the element-wise addition $T_1 \oplus T_2$ and the truncated convolution $T_1 \otimes T_2$ of tensors, respectively.*

From Lemma 3, the next lemma follows.

Lemma 4 (Lifting lemma). *If $(R, +_R, \cdot_R, 0_R, 1_R)$ is a (commutative) semiring, then the structure $(R^{\mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]}, \oplus, \otimes, \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1})$ is a (commutative) semiring.*

Reduction from MT to Unconstrained ADTC. We present a reduction from the MODEL BEHAVIOR TENSOR problem to the unconstrained ADTC problem over the tensor semiring $R^{\mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]}$.

Definition 7 (Reduction from MT to unconstrained ADTC). Given an instance $Q' = (\Delta, \alpha, \sigma)$ of the MT and input data $D = (S, y)$, we let $\alpha_* : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow R^{\mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]}$ be the aggregation operator defined as: for any (t, S) in \mathcal{S} , $\alpha_*(t, S)$ is given by the singleton tensor $[i = \mathbf{k}]v$ in $R^{\mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]}$ such that $\mathbf{k} := \sigma(t, S)$ and $v := \alpha(t, S)$. The instance of the unconstrained ADTC problem consists of the query $Q = (\Delta, \alpha_*)$ and the data D .

² Unlike the cyclic polynomials $R[(x_j)_d] / \langle x^{m_j} - 1 \rangle_{j=1}^d$ typical in signal processing, we use truncated polynomials $R[(x_j)_d] / \langle x^{m_j} \rangle_{j=1}^d$ in relation to the tensors in $R^{\mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]}$.

Unconstrained ADTC computes the \oplus -sum of $\alpha_*(t, S)$ over $t \in \mathcal{M}_\Delta$. Combining Def. 3 and Def. 7, we obtain Lemma 5 and Theorem 2 below.

Lemma 5 (Correctness of the reduction). *Let R be any commutative semiring. For any rank- d model tensor query $Q = (\Delta, \alpha, \sigma)$, the solution $\text{MT}[Q, D]$ over the tensor semiring $(R^{\mathbb{N}^{[m]}}, \oplus, \otimes, \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1})$ coincides with the solution of the ADTC problem using the constructed unconstrained query $Q' = (\Delta, \alpha_*)$.*

Theorem 2 (Complexity of MT). *Under Assump. 1, the MODEL BEHAVIOR TENSOR problem over R can be solved in $O^*(n^{O(\Delta)} \cdot m_*^{2d} \cdot t_R)$ time and $O^*(m_*^d \cdot s_R)$ space, where $Q = (\Delta, \alpha, \sigma)$ is a rank- d tensor query, $D = (S, y)$ is input data, and m_* is maximum range value.*

Proof. Combining the algorithm EMT and the reduction of Def. 7, the correctness follows from Lem. 2 and Lem. 5. For time complexity, consider any rank- d tensors T, T_1, T_0 . Since $V(T) = O(m_*^d)$, we see that T can be stored in $O(m_*^d \cdot s_R)$ space. Moreover, tensor operations $[i = k]v$, $T_1 \oplus T_0$, and $T_1 \otimes T_0$ of Def. 6 can be implemented to run within $O((V(T_1) \cdot V(T_0)) \cdot t_R) = O(m_*^{2d} \cdot t_R)$ time. Combining these quantities, the time complexity follows from Theorem 1 in the unconstrained case. \square

3.4 Putting It Together

Given an answer $T = \text{MT}[Q_{\text{mt}}, D]$ for the reduced query $Q_{\text{mt}} = (\Delta, \alpha, \sigma)$, the answer $\text{ADTC}[Q, D]$ for the original query $Q = (\Delta, \alpha, \sigma, \phi[\sigma])$ is obtained by summing up the weights $T(\mathbf{k})$ over all \mathbf{k} satisfying $\phi[\mathbf{k}]$. From Theorem 2, we have the main theorem.

Theorem 3 (Complexity of ADTC with constraint). *Under Assump. 1, given a rank- d query $Q = (\Delta, \alpha, \sigma, \phi[\sigma])$ and an input data $D = (S, y)$, the general ADTC problem can be solved in the asymptotically same time and space complexities as Theorem 2.*

Finally, the cell size s_R and operation time t_R over R depend on the maximum entry size M in T . In the worst case, M reaches $O(2^\Delta)$ if all $|\mathcal{M}_\Delta| = n^{\Theta(2^\Delta)}$ trees fall into a single cell, yielding $s_R = \Theta(\log |\mathcal{M}_\Delta|) = \Theta(2^\Delta \log n)$. In practice, however, appropriate hyperparameters like depth Δ and minsup effectively bound M (Sec. 5).

4 Extensions

In this section, we introduce extensions to algorithm EMT in Sec. 3 that enable the use of complex, nonlinear metrics as well as selection and sampling of concrete models.

4.1 Extensions to Contingency Tables and Nonlinear Model Metrics

Global analysis often involves complex *nonlinear metrics* [13]. To address this, we use *rational metrics*, functions defined by a fraction $P(x)/Q(x)$ of multivariate polynomials over primitive metrics (Sec. 2.4). Many statistical scores [30] can be expressed as rational metrics. Below, we introduce rational metrics definable in terms of 2-way and

Fig. 3: (a) Model profiles generated by ADTC on the `adult` dataset showing the structural distribution of near-optimal models (Sec. 5.3). (b) Dashboard interface for selecting a model from the cross-table to display its decision tree (Sec. 4.2).

3-way contingency tables [20]. Let indices $i, j, k \in \{0, 1\}$ represent the *true label* y , *predicted label* $\hat{y} = f_t(x)$, and *sensitive attribute* z in a dataset S , respectively. For a tree t , the 2-way table entry $N_{ij}(t; S)$ is defined as $\sum_{x \in S} \mathbf{1}[(y(x) = i) \wedge (f_t(x) = j)]$. Entries $N_{ijk}(t; S)$ of a 3-way table are defined analogously. Cell probabilities are then easily derived (e.g., true positives $tp = N_{11}/|S|$).

Using the contingency tables, we can formulate a variety of score functions [30], such as the F1-score [20] and Equalized odds (EOdd) [19] as follows:

- (i) *F1-score*: $F1(t; S) = 2N_{11}/(2N_{11} + N_{01} + N_{10})$, and
- (ii) *Equalized odds*: $EOdd(t; S) = |(N_{011}/N_{0*1}) - (N_{010}/N_{0*0})| + |(N_{111}/N_{1*1}) - (N_{110}/N_{1*0})|$, where $N_{i*k} = N_{i1k} + N_{i0k}$ denotes the marginal count for true label i and sensitive attribute k .

As a practical optimization for ADTC, we minimize the tensor dimensionality by isolating and maintaining *model-independent metrics* outside a tensor T . For instance, the metric N_{i*k} is model-independent for any $i, k \in \{0, 1, *\}$ because its index $j = \hat{y}$ is the constant $*$. Similarly, the *counts of all, positive, and sensitive examples*, specifically $N_{***} = |S|$, $N_{1**} = N_{y=1}$, and $N_{**1} = N_{z=1}$, fall into this class. This leads to significant savings in both memory and construction time.

4.2 Selection and Sampling of Supporting Models

By modifying the algorithm EMT, we can efficiently implement the selection and random sampling of decision trees that support the value of ADTC(R) in a model behavior tensor T . For this purpose, we use the technique of a *semiring extension* for selection and sampling, recently proposed by Goral *et al.* [17] (see also [4] for a similar technique). To do this, we construct the product semiring $\mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{T}$ of the count semiring \mathbb{N} and the pseudo semiring \mathbb{T} of decision tree syntaxes. For each index $\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{N}[\mathbf{m}]$, the

Fig. 4: Scalability of ADTC relative to data size (Sec. 5.2).

k -th cell of T holds a pair $T(\mathbf{k}) = (N_{\mathbf{k}}, t_{\mathbf{k}})$ consisting of a count $N_{\mathbf{k}} \in \mathbb{N}$ and a tree $t_{\mathbf{k}} \in \mathcal{M}_{\Delta}$. The first semiring $\mathbb{N} = (\mathbb{N}, +, \times)$ maintains the count $N_{\mathbf{k}}$ of trees falling into the k -th cell of T , $N_{\mathbf{k}} = T(\mathbf{k}) \in \mathbb{N}$, for all indices $\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{N}[m]$. On the other hand, the second pseudo semiring $(\mathbb{T}, +, \{\langle f, \cdot, \cdot \rangle\}_{f \in F})$ holds a tree t uniformly sampled by the probability $P_{\mathbf{k}} = N_{\mathbf{k}}/N_{\text{total}} \in [0, 1]$, where $N_{\text{total}} = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} N_{\mathbf{k}} = |\mathcal{M}_{\Delta}|$ is the total count. Since the rest of the construction is almost the same as Goral *et al.* [17], we omit the details. We implemented this function in our software `emtrees`. Fig. 3 shows our dashboard interface, rendering a randomly sampled tree from the associated cell.

5 Experimental Evaluation

We evaluate ADTC on real-world data to demonstrate its scalability and utility in providing a transparent and rigorous analysis of high-performing decision trees.

5.1 Setup

Dataset. We use the UCI `adult` dataset (32,129 data) as a standard benchmark for research on fairness and predictive multiplicity, aiming to predict whether annual income exceeds \$50,000 using mixed categorical and continuous variables.

Measurement Protocol. *Computational cost* is evaluated using: (i) `time` (execution time in seconds); (ii) `cell_scan` (total number of cells scanned as a platform-independent cost); and (iii) `num_cells` (non-zero entries in the resulting tensors). *For parameter configurations*, we use the following settings unless otherwise stated: `maxdep = 5` (maximum depth), `nbins = 7` (number of bins in discretization of numerical features), `relminsup = 0.15` (relative minimum support), and `siz = 6` (tree size). *Data scalability analysis* varies `n_data` from 40 to 32,129 (all data). *Structural complexity analysis* scales `maxdep` and `siz` proportionally. *Constraint relaxation analysis* varies `siz` from 1 to 16 with `n_data = 640` and `maxdep = 4`. **Environment:** The system `emtrees` is implemented in Python 3.12 and executed on an Apple M1 Pro PC (16GB memory, macOS 15.7.1). The source code is publicly available.³

³ `emtrees`: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20842908>

Fig. 5: Impact of maximum depth on efficiency (Sec. 5.2).

Fig. 6: Effect of tree size on resolution (Sec. 5.2).

5.2 Scalability and Computational Efficiency

Our empirical evaluation demonstrates that ADTC exhibits scalable and stable behavior across all parameters. Our program ran within several minutes on mid-sized datasets such as UCI mushroom, adult,⁴ and COMPAS⁵ under the parameter settings above.

Scalability with input size. As shown in Fig. 4, the runtime and `cell_scan` follow near-linear trends on a log-log scale, confirming polynomial complexity relative to n_{data} . Even with an 800-fold increase in data size, the runtime remains manageable at 255.79 seconds for the full dataset (1.1×10^9 cells scanned). Concurrently, `num_cells` grows proportionally, indicating a more refined model profile for larger datasets.

Impact of structural constraints. We evaluate how structural expansion affects efficiency. *Tree depth:* Fig. 5 shows that the `cell_scan` grows as depth Δ (`maxdep`) relaxes, reflecting the expansion of the search space. Despite the doubly exponential nature of the syntactical space, the operations remain stable, reaching $\approx 2.0 \times 10^7$ scanned cells at $\Delta = 5$. *Tree size constraint:* Fig. 6 shows that relaxing the tree size constraint s (`siz`) increases `num_cells`, yielding a more detailed model profile. Stabilization of `cell_scan` at higher `siz` values suggests that model tensors efficiently aggregate properties once structural complexity is captured, incurring minimal overhead.

⁴ <https://archive.ics.uci.edu>

⁵ <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/danofer/compass>

Fig. 7: Model profiles generated by ADTC on the `adult` dataset. Horizontal axes denote accuracy; vertical axes represent (c) EOdd and (d) EOpp gaps. Higher values are better for accuracy, whereas lower values indicate better fairness (Sec. 5.4).

5.3 Impact of Model Complexity on the Rashomon Set

We analyze the structural properties of near-optimal models by examining the relationship between model size (`siz`) and depth (`maxdep`). We focus on high-performing models with $\text{acc} \geq 0.749$ in the Rashomon set. Fig. 3 (a) (in Sec. 4.2) reveals that 352,768 top-performing trees cluster in the range of depth 4 and sizes $4 \sim 5$, showing strong structural consistency. This highlights the trade-off between interpretability and predictive performance under diverse deployment scenarios. See Sec. 4.2 for details on the dashboard shown in Fig. 3 (b).

5.4 Trade-off Analysis between Accuracy and Fairness

To demonstrate how ADTC supports evidence-based model selection, Fig. 1 (in Sec. 1) and Fig. 7 show the distribution of the 34,706 models extracted from the Rashomon set on the `adult` dataset. These distributions are evaluated with respect to *accuracy* (`acc`), *F1-score* (`F1`), and fairness metrics, including *demographic parity* (`DP`), *equalized odds* (`EOdd`), and *equal opportunity* (`EOpp`) [19]. The obtained cross-tables provides a rigorous model profile that serves as objective evidence for model selection.

For instance, in Fig. 7 (a), our framework identifies a *large cluster of 15,340 models* in the bin with the *highest accuracy* ($\text{acc} \in [0.765, 0.831]$) and *low fairness error* $\text{EOdd} \in [-0.029, 0.086]$, while revealing a *smaller cluster of 688 models* with the *same accuracy but significantly higher fairness error* ($\text{EOdd} \in [0.886, 1.000]$). Conversely, many models with moderate accuracy exhibit high fairness disparity, such as the 10,906 models with $\text{acc} \in [0.566, 0.633]$ and high EOdd. By providing a complete landscape of the Rashomon set, ADTC facilitates evidence-based model selection, allowing practitioners to prioritize high-accuracy models with minimal fairness disparity from numerous candidates rather than relying on a single heuristic output.

5.5 Assessment of Preprocessing

In Fig. 2 (in Sec. 1), we show the model profiles on *accuracy* (`acc`) and *balanced accuracy* (`bacc`) [30] of near-optimal models generated by ADTC on the original `adult` dataset and its class-balanced dataset. They show a discrepancy between `acc` and `bacc` in the original dataset, which is successfully calibrated in the balanced dataset.

6 Conclusion

This paper presents ADTC, a formal framework for the global assessment of decision tree spaces. Through the use of model behavior tensors and an algebraic formulation, we provide a scalable methodology for evidence-based model selection, enabling a rigorous analysis of the landscape of interpretable models.

Theoretically, this research contributes by formulating the ADTC problem and developing efficient algorithms that establish complexity upper bounds over general semirings. For future work, extending the ADTC framework to other interpretable models is a promising direction, building upon existing enumeration techniques for *LASSO models* [18], *support vector machines* [21], and *rule lists with profile construction* [25]. Finally, we will investigate the computational complexity of ADTC relative to standard counting classes like Valiant’s $\#P$ [31] and the semiring-based class $NP_\infty(R)$ recently proposed in [5]. Our tensor-manipulation software, `emtrees`, introduced in Sec. 3 and Sec. 4, is publicly available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20842908>.

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